

DINI/nestor-Workshops RDM in CRCs and research groups

Thank you for your willingness to complete the questionnaire on the implementation of data management in Collaborative Research Centers (CRCs) and Research Units. The questionnaire is intended to record the status quo of data management in CRCs and research groups and serves to prepare the DINI/nestor event on research data management in CRCs and research groups on December 2 and 3, 2024 in Cologne. The event is organized together with the RDM state initiatives HeFDI (Hesse) and SaxFDM (Saxony) as well as the University of Cologne.

For the survey, we are mainly using questions that we have already asked information infrastructure projects in CRCs in 2013 and 2018. Our aim is to be able to trace the development over time. At the same time, we want to determine which topics are suitable for the two sessions on December 3. The results of the survey will be presented at the event on December 2 and 3, 2024 in Cologne.

The data is collected using the RedCap tool, which is hosted at the Philipps University of Marburg. The raw data remains on the servers of Philipps-Universität Marburg. The DINI/nestor workshop team processes the aggregated data. If you have any questions about the survey, please contact hefdi@uni-marburg.de.

How is your data management sub-project embedded within the CRC or research group? Describe briefly to what extent it is, for example, a separate sub-project, an INF project or a Z- or S-project (in Collaborative Research Centers) or whether it is part of a central coordination of the CRC or the research group.

What tasks do you take on for the other sub-projects? (multiple answers possible)

- Database / repository / data integration platform
- Collaborative working environment
- Data management
- Advice / support / training for data management
- Development / implementation / provision of tools
- Long-term archiving of (meta-)data
- Publication of research data
- Development of standards (selection of data formats, metadata standards, etc.)
- IT administration
- Research
- Subsequent use of research data
- Data analysis
- Digitalization of analogue research data
- Other, namely...

Please explain "Other"

What challenges do you face in your practical work? (multiple answers possible)

- Heterogeneity of research data
- Heterogeneity of methods
- Technical challenges
- Resources (personnel, IT, etc.)
- Acceptance of RDM measures (by researchers)
- Inadequate documentation and allocation of metadata
- Later start of data management in the INF project or in the research group compared to the research projects
- Legal issues, such as rights of use and/or licensing of research data
- Lack of qualified personnel for data management in the INF project or in the research groupOther, namely...
- Other, namely...

Please explain "Other"

Which measures do you use to support data management?
(multiple answers possible)

- Hardware
- Provision of repositories, other databases or data integration platforms
- Advice and recommendation of existing repositories, other databases or data integration platforms
- Support for the generation of metadata
- Finding and selecting suitable metadata schemas
- Access to data resources and/or hardware of the CRC or the research group
- Provision of solutions for collaborative working
- Provision of DOIs
- Networking of software solutions through the development of interfaces
- Other, namely...

Please explain "Other"

Are you developing own software solutions for handling data in the subprojects?

- Yes
- No

Are these developments open source?

- Yes
- No

With which specifications and guidelines do you support data management?
(multiple answers possible)

- Data management policies
- Policies / guidelines on data protection and data security
- Development and provision of terms of use templates
- Metadata schemas / documentation schemas
- Obligation to store data in a repository or similar
- Orientation towards the needs / habits of the users
- Other, namely...

Please explain "Other"

What human resources are available for data management in the CRC / research group?
(please specify in FTE)

How much direct costs are available for data management in the CRC / research group? (Please specify in €)

Are supra-regional RDM services (re-)used/ for the CRC or research group? These include, for example, services from RDM state initiatives, from consortia of the National Research Data Infrastructure, from European providers (Elixir, ...) and others

- Yes
- No

Which initiatives use RDM services?
(multiple answers possible)

- Services of country initiatives
- Services of consortia of the National Research Data Infrastructure
- Services from the European context, e.g. Elixir
- Other, namely...

Please explain "Other"

Which services are predominantly used?

Are there other collaborations with initiatives that offer RDM services/infrastructure?

- Yes
- No

With which of these initiatives do you cooperate?
(multiple answers possible)

- Local RDM service of your own research institution/library/computing center
- RDM national initiatives
- NFDI consortia
- Elixir
- Other, namely...

Please explain "Other"

Is there a need within the CRC or research group to exchange data between subprojects?

- Yes
- No

To what extent is data exchange supported by the INF project or data management?
